

The Purposes of Measurement Uncertainty

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Abstract

It is now more than 40 years since the BIPM outlined the current harmonised approach to the expression of uncertainty in measurement, and 30 years since the publication of the *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement*. Despite several decades of use and application to a wide variety of measurements, there remains a lack of clarity about the purpose of measurement uncertainty. The lack of clarity is most clearly reflected in the inconsistency in the way uncertainty is used and reported. The lack of a clear statement of purpose is also an impediment to the teaching of good measurement practice. This paper investigates a range of applications of measurement uncertainty to identify and illustrate the purposes of measurement uncertainty, and to understand its proper usage and reporting. Two broad purposes for uncertainty are identified: one relating to decision making and utilising expanded uncertainties to characterise the range of values attributable to a measurand, and one relating to the modelling of dispersive effects in measurements and utilising standard uncertainties as the measure of dispersion. Expanded uncertainties are used at the ends of traceability chains to make inferences about the measurand and ensure decisions can be made with appropriate confidence. Standard uncertainties are parameters in measurement models characterising the unpredictable aspects of measurement processes and are propagated along traceability chains to ensure meaningful inferences and decision making. Suggestions for improvements to uncertainty guides and for the usage and reporting of uncertainty are provided.

1. Introduction

It is now more than 40 years since the BIPM (Bureau International des Poids et Mesures) announced and outlined the current harmonised approach to the expression of uncertainty in measurement [1], and 30 years since the publication of the first *Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement*, the GUM [2]. The GUM is a remarkably successful document, having been responsible for a near universal and worldwide harmonisation of measurement uncertainty practice. Yet, despite the decades of use of the GUM approach, despite extensive research and analysis of uncertainty in metrological measurements, and despite the integration of measurement uncertainty into hundreds of documentary standards and parts of the legislation of many countries, there is nowhere in any of the BIPM guidance documents a clear statement about the purpose of measurement uncertainty.

Why is an understanding of purpose important? Most obviously, without a clearly understood purpose, it may be difficult for users to be sure that an uncertainty statement, or method of assessing uncertainty, or application of measurement uncertainty, is fit for purpose. Evidence of a problem is most often seen in the confusion about whether to report standard uncertainties

or expanded uncertainties in metrological documents. For example, most calibration certificates from ISO/IEC 17025-accredited laboratories report an expanded uncertainty, yet second- and third-tier laboratories only ever use the standard uncertainty in their uncertainty calculations—so why is the expanded uncertainty reported? ISO/IEC 17025: *General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories* [3], provides no guidance in this respect. A notable exception to common practice is found at the BIPM, whose policy is to issue all calibration reports using standard uncertainties only [4, Sec 13.3]—why is there a difference?

Similar confusion can often be found in scientific papers where authors are unsure about whether to report standard uncertainties or expanded uncertainties. A need for guidance is becoming especially important as the metrology community develops protocols for the digital reporting of measurements [5], with the accompanying risk of freezing poor or confused practice into standardised digital reporting formats.

In the experience of the authors, all of whom have been involved in the technical assessments of the competence of staff in accredited laboratories, the lack of a clear purpose for measurement uncertainty underlies some of

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the problems with the training and motivation of staff performing calculations critical to the traceability of their and their clients' measurements. To many, in the absence of an understanding of the purpose, uncertainty calculation must seem like a ritual for which any token effort will suffice.

The aim of this paper is to clearly identify the purposes of measurement uncertainty. First, to establish the context of the discussion, we review what various guidance documents say in relation to the purpose of measurement uncertainty, focusing on the recommendations of the GUM and its supplements. We then consider the most common applications of measurement uncertainty with the aim of identifying its purposes. Finally, we summarise our conclusions, suggest improved definitions for the meaning of uncertainty, and provide guidelines for the reporting of measurement uncertainty.

2. What do the Guides Say?

The BIPM website provides access to the latest version of the GUM [6], and the five supplements to the GUM [7–11]. None of the documents provide an explicit statement of the purpose of measurement uncertainty. Curiously, the GUM does state its own purpose: to promote full information on how uncertainty statements are arrived at, and to provide a basis for the international comparison of measurement results. The GUM also makes the following introductory statement:

When reporting the result of a measurement of a physical quantity, it is obligatory that some quantitative indication of the quality of the result be given so that those who use it can assess its reliability. Without such an indication, measurement results cannot be compared, either among themselves or with reference values given in a specification or standard. It is therefore necessary that there be a readily implemented, easily understood, and generally accepted procedure for characterizing the quality of a result of a measurement, that is, for evaluating and expressing its *uncertainty*.

These claims seem grossly overstated. Why is a quantitative indication of the quality of a result obligatory? Why can't measurement results be compared in the absence of uncertainties? Why is it necessary for there to be an accepted procedure for calculating measurement uncertainty? The answers are not obvious, and no explanation is offered.

Similar statements can be found in most uncertainty guides and, typically, none of them answer any of the 'why' questions. The GUM does give a long list of examples where uncertainty may be applied: "...maintaining quality control and quality assurance in production; complying with and enforcing laws and regulations; conducting basic research, and applied research and development, in science and engineering; calibrating standards and instruments and performing

tests throughout a national measurement system in order to achieve traceability to national standards; developing, maintaining, and comparing international and national physical reference standards, including reference materials". This is useful information, but there is no indication of how uncertainty is used in these applications, why it is in any sense obligatory, why it must be calculated using an accepted procedure, or why it is required when comparing measurements.

The GUM Supplement 4, *An introduction to the GUM and related documents* [9], has a long discussion about what measurement uncertainty is and identifies some of its properties, but it is still not clear why we need it. It does make the following statement (bold font added):

Measurement uncertainty is a general concept associated with any measurement and can be used in **professional decision processes** as well as judging attributes in many domains, both theoretical and experimental.

This is the nearest any of the GUM documents come to a statement of purpose.

The GUM Supplement 6, *The role of measurement uncertainty in conformity assessment* [11], gives the clearest examples of how uncertainty is used, although it provides no statement of purpose. We briefly discuss the case of conformity assessment in a later section.

3. Applications of Uncertainty

3.1 Physical Models

In probability theory, the central limit theorem (CLT) establishes that the distribution of the sum of independent random variables, including variables from differing distributions, tends towards a normal distribution. Exceptions to the CLT are where variables are drawn from distributions for which the variance does not exist (notably the Cauchy–Lorentz distribution and some Pareto distributions). The real-world consequence of the CLT is that a very large number of naturally occurring random phenomena have a normal distribution.

The probability density function (PDF) for the normal distribution can be written as

$$p(x) = \frac{1}{\sigma\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(\frac{-(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad (1)$$

where μ and σ^2 are, respectively, the mean and variance of the distribution. The mean is the centre of mass of the distribution and the standard deviation (the square root of the variance) is a measure of the width of the distribution, or equivalently, a measure of the dispersion of the physical effect described by the distribution.

The degree to which different physical effects follow the normal distribution varies. Johnson noise, the electrical voltage or current noise induced by the random motion of electrons in conductors, follows a normal distribution

exactly. The variance of the noise voltage, V_T , is related to the resistance of the conductor, R , the temperature of the conductor, T , the Boltzmann constant, k , and the bandwidth over which the noise is measured, Δf , by

$$\overline{V_T^2} = 4kTR\Delta f. \quad (2)$$

Johnson noise is one of many phenomena described by the fluctuation dissipation theorem [12], which relates the dissipative effects in all linear dissipative systems to thermally induced fluctuations. Other well-known examples are Brownian motion and blackbody radiation.

Another class of systems that follow a normal distribution exactly is systems exhibiting shot or Poisson noise, which occurs when quantised objects such as electrons, photons, molecules, ions, etc. arrive at a collection site with random arrival times [13]. The effect is a major source of noise in optical detectors (random arrival of photons) and semiconductors (random arrival of electrons), for example.

Less ideal examples of naturally-occurring normally-distributed effects include acoustic road noise under vehicles, the noise from the breaking of bubbles in a fizzy drink, pressure fluctuations in the atmosphere due to weather, temperature fluctuations in temperature-controlled systems, etc.—the number of effects is practically endless. In physical models, the dispersive effects are nearly always characterised by the variance or the standard deviation. This parameterisation is especially evident in the specifications of measuring instruments, sensors, and calibration media, where noise is an important factor in performance.

In systems where the physical effects combine as a product rather than a sum (as described so far), the fluctuations follow a lognormal distribution [14], a close relative of the normal distribution in which the logarithm of the random variable is distributed normally. Lognormal distributions are common in chemical and biological systems, for example. In these cases, too, the variance or the standard deviation are the most universal and convenient measures of dispersion.

There are a few cases where dispersion is measured in other ways. Probably the most common example is truncation error or quantisation error, which has a uniform distribution and may be characterised by the semi-range just as easily as the variance. Another example is the class of errors with an arcsine distribution, commonly occurring in rotational systems, that may be characterised by the maximum or semi-range as easily as the variance or the RMS (root mean square) value. In systems where one of the distributions with no variance occurs (commonly in time, frequency, and spectral measurements), other measures of dispersion may be used, such as the FWHM (full width at half maximum) of spectral lines or the Allan variance. Otherwise, in most physical models, including measurement models, the variance or standard deviation is the parameter used to characterise dispersion.

3.2 Propagation of Uncertainty

One of the simplest, yet most powerful, results of probability theory is that for linear combinations of independent random variables, the means, μ , and variances, σ^2 , add linearly [15]. That is, for any linear combination of random variables, x, v, w, \dots

$$y = ax + bv + cw + \dots, \quad (3)$$

where a, b, c, \dots are constants, the mean is

$$\mu_y = a\mu_x + b\mu_v + c\mu_w + \dots, \quad (4)$$

and the variance is

$$\sigma_y^2 = a^2\sigma_x^2 + b^2\sigma_v^2 + c^2\sigma_w^2 + \dots. \quad (5)$$

This remarkable result applies to all combinations of random variables for which the variance exists, including cases when the variables have differing distributions. No other measure of the width of a distribution has this property. For those building measurement models to evaluate the cumulative effect of different dispersive processes, the utility and power of the result is obvious. Indeed, it is so important that the authors of the first GUM chose to use the relation (5) as the backbone of the GUM [6, Sec. 5] and chose to use the standard deviation as the primary measure of uncertainty.

Equation (5) is exact only for linear combinations of random variables, as in equation (3). However, where the dispersive effects are small in relation to non-linearities, the effects are very well approximated by Taylor series, and the equation,

$$\sigma_y^2 = \left(\frac{dy}{du}\right)^2 \sigma_u^2 + \left(\frac{dy}{dv}\right)^2 \sigma_v^2 + \left(\frac{dy}{dw}\right)^2 \sigma_w^2 + \dots, \quad (6)$$

proves to be a very satisfactory approximation [16, Chapters 7 and 8].

3.3 Consensus Values

The recent CODATA (the Committee on Data for Science and Technology) special adjustment of the fundamental constants preceding the SI redefinition is an example of the many determinations of consensus values carried out by CODATA committees [17]. In the simplest cases, such as for a physical property of some useful material, the consensus value may be determined from the weighted mean, \bar{y} , of the set of results, y_i , produced by different methods or different researchers:

$$\bar{y} = \sum_{i=1}^N w_i y_i, \quad (7)$$

where w_i are the weights applied to each result. If we suppose the uncertainties in the measurements are standard deviations, σ_i , of measurement errors, then it is easily shown that the mean with the minimum variance is achieved when the weights are proportional to the

reciprocals of the respective variances of the contributing results:

$$\bar{y} = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} \right)^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{y_i}{\sigma_i^2}, \quad (8)$$

where the leading multiplying factor normalises the weights so that they add to 1. The multiplying factor is also the variance in the mean. Equation (8) is a statistical estimator that is the best linear unbiased estimator (BLUE) [18].

In some experiments, the problem is to determine a value for a model parameter not directly observable from a single measurement. A spectacular example is the determination of the mass of the black hole at the centre of the Milky Way from a series of observations, taken over the last 20 years or so, of the stars orbiting the black hole. The BLUE of the model parameter is obtained by the method of weighted least squares, which determines a number, ρ , of parameter values, a, b, c, \dots , that minimise the mean-squared difference, χ^2 , between the model predictions and N observations, using the variances in the measurements as the weights:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{1}{N - \rho} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{1}{\sigma_i^2} [y(x_i : a, b, c, \dots) - y_i]^2. \quad (9)$$

For the CODATA adjustments of fundamental physical constants, which involve a simultaneous determination of the values of up to 160 inter-related consensus values [19], the method of constrained least squares is used, again using the variances in the measurements as the weights (see [20] for detail).

3.4 Conformity Testing

Everyone makes allowances for measurement uncertainty, often many times a day, though we are usually unaware of it: we fill the car with petrol before it runs out; we arrive at appointments before the scheduled times; and we buy a little more material than we need to finish a construction or assembly. We err on the side of caution. These are examples of the types of decision-making processes occurring with conformity assessment. Conformity assessment is any activity undertaken to determine whether a product, process, system, person, or body fulfills specified requirements [11]. Let's consider an example in detail to see how measurement uncertainty is used.

Suppose a commercial baker is selling biscuits in packets labelled as containing 200 g net weight. Under consumer protection legislation (known as the Average Quantity System in many countries [21, 22]), the baker is required to ensure that the relative frequency of underfilling of packets of biscuits is below some specified upper limit. Typically, each full packet is weighed as it comes off the production line and is corrected for the average weight of the empty packets to determine the net weight. The uncertainty in the net weight arises from the combination of the errors in the measurement of gross weight and the

variations in the weights of the empty packets. If the baker approves for sale all packets with a measured net weight exceeding 200 g, then there is a finite, perhaps significant, probability of approving underweight packets. This situation is illustrated in Figure 1(a) for a packet with a true net weight of 198 g. The unpredictability of measurement errors causes dispersion in measured net weights, as indicated in the figure by the curve representing the normal PDF centred on 198 g, the width of which is characterised by the standard uncertainty. The shaded area above 200 g therefore indicates the probability of approving the underweight packet for sale.

To reduce the probability of approving underweight packets, the baker raises the acceptance limit above 200 g by an amount corresponding to an appropriate multiple of the standard uncertainty, corresponding to the level of risk that the baker is willing to take. The added amount, shaded lightly in yellow in Figure 1(b), is the guard band.

In Figure 1(b), the darker shaded area represents the probability that a packet of exactly 200 g net weight will be approved for sale. Setting the acceptance limit so that this probability matches the legislated maximum relative frequency ensures that the legal requirements are met. In this way, knowledge of uncertainty enables the baker to adjust the quality control process to achieve any desired (low) probability of approving an underweight packet.

Figure 1: (a) Without a guard band, there is a high probability (shaded area) of approving an underweight 198 g packet for sale. (b) To reduce and control the probability of approving underweight packets, the baker includes a guard band in the decision-making process to account for the uncertainty in the net weights of the packets.

The baker's conformity assessment involves several costs. First, with the guard band in place, the baker sells packets that, on average, exceed the stated 200 g net weight, so is giving away product. Second, the increased number of rejected packets, which may be sold as seconds or destroyed, adds to the baker's financial losses. But on the positive side of the ledger, the baker is reducing, perhaps eliminating, the risk of being prosecuted for selling underweight goods. The baker has traded a small easily accounted cost against the much more significant and damaging cost of a possible prosecution and loss of reputation.

From a statistical perspective, the baker is lowering the probability of false positives (approving underweight packets—a Type 1 statistical error) at the expense of increasing the probability of the false negatives (falsely rejecting packets exceeding 200 g—a Type 2 statistical error). To optimise the decision-making process, an objective estimate of the uncertainty (neither optimistic nor pessimistic) and well-quantified estimates of the costs and risks are required.

Similar cost–risk compromises involving incommensurate risks and costs occur with almost all measurement-based decisions. Other examples include: pasteurisation, where microbial kill rate and health risks are traded for food quality; petrochemical plants, where productivity at high temperatures is traded against plant life; and engineering structures, where building cost is traded against survival in extreme events. The optimal balance of the risks and costs is usually highly specific to the situation.

Conformity assessments also occur in three forms. As here, a producer is managing risks and costs. Suppose, instead, that a consumer affairs inspector acting on behalf of consumers has been informed that the baker is selling underweight goods. The inspector samples and weighs packets from shop shelves, but this time includes a guard band below the 200 g specified weight according to the uncertainties in his or her own measurements. The guard band must be below the tolerance limit to be sure that the packets are indeed underweight, and to have high confidence in any decision to prosecute the baker. In drug manufacture, a producer may impose both upper and lower guard bands for measurements of the amount of active ingredient in tablets or bottles.

In all cases, the decision-making process can be prescribed as a requirement on the measurement result, plus or minus some multiple of the standard deviation, to be below or above the tolerance limit. That is, there is a correspondence between the width of the guard band and an expanded uncertainty equal to half of the corresponding width of the confidence interval for the value of the measurand. Note too, that successful management of conformity tests depends on an objective, ideally unbiased, value for the standard uncertainty, and possibly on information about the number of degrees of freedom associated with the standard deviation and the type of distribution (often assumed to be normal). Without such information, the decision maker may be

unable to correctly optimise the conformity assessment and make decisions with appropriate confidence and according to needs.

3.5 Proficiency Tests and Measurement Comparisons

Proficiency tests are an example of a measurement comparison concerned with the assessment of the performance of the participants through the statistical evaluation of their results of measurements of a shared artefact. This is just one of the possible purposes of measurement comparisons. Other purposes include the identification of problems in laboratories, establishing effectiveness and comparability of test or measurement methods, the provision of additional confidence to laboratory customers, validation of uncertainty claims, and the education of participating laboratories.

In most comparisons, the performance scores are evaluated as ratios of the difference between a reported result and an assigned or consensus value for the artefact, and an estimate of the uncertainty of the difference, variously called z scores, z' scores, E_n numbers, or ζ scores, depending on the detailed purpose and design of the comparison [23]. For example, the ζ score measures a participant's ability to provide results within their claimed uncertainty of the assigned value:

$$\zeta_i = \frac{x_i - x_{pt}}{(u_i^2 + u_{pt}^2)^{1/2}}, \quad (10)$$

where x_i and u_i are the reported result and standard uncertainty for participant i , and x_{pt} and u_{pt} are the value and uncertainty assigned to the artefact.

Once the scores are computed in this form, an action scheme is applied to determine consequential actions [21]:

- a result that gives $|\zeta_i| \leq 2.0$ is considered acceptable;
- a result that gives $2.0 < |\zeta_i| < 3.0$ is considered to provide a warning signal;
- a result that gives $|\zeta_i| \geq 3.0$ is considered unacceptable or a signal for action.

The break points in the action scheme are linked to the coverage factors for a normal distribution: a warning signal is given if the probability of obtaining a result as extreme as observed is below 5%, and action is required if the probability of obtaining such a result is below 0.3%.

In reality, the underlying distributions of the measurement errors are usually not well known, so the assumption of normality is an approximation. As with the conformity test, there is a ready interpretation of the action scheme in terms of expanded uncertainties—a participant should report a result within the combined expanded uncertainty of the artefact's assigned value and the participant's measurement of it.

3.6 Hypothesis Testing

Most decision-making processes involving measurements have a formal equivalent in the form of a statistical test, part of which includes the mathematical construction of an interval within which the value of the measurand is expected to lie. There are many types of statistical tests, and one of the most used is the Neyman–Pearson hypothesis test [15, 24]. The usual procedure is to formulate two hypotheses: one is called the null hypothesis (think of this as situation normal), and the other is the alternative hypothesis, which might be that there is some unmodelled effect in the measurements. The analyst considers the assumptions about the distribution of the measurements and designs a statistical test to compare one hypothesis against the other—does the result lie outside the expected interval? No test is conclusive—there is always a finite probability of drawing the wrong conclusion—so strictly, hypothesis tests provide evidence for or against the hypotheses rather than firm conclusions. Usually, the strength of evidence is presented either as a probability—for example, “there is a probability of less than 5% that this result has occurred by chance” (given the null hypothesis)—or as a multiple of a standard deviation, perhaps 2-sigma.

For scientific hypothesis testing, such as ‘confirming’ the existence of new fundamental particles, 5-sigma is often used (equivalent to a probability of less than 0.000 035% that the observations are explained by chance). As with conformity tests and proficiency tests, we see decision making based on probabilities or an equivalent multiple of a standard deviation.

4. Discussion and Conclusions

The six applications of measurement uncertainty discussed above fall into two broad classes. The first three applications are examples of modelling, where the standard deviation appears as a model parameter characterising the dispersion caused by some effect within the measurement. In the last three applications, which are examples of decision making, expanded uncertainties, characterising the range of values attributable to a measurand, are used to make a trade-off between the probabilities of Type 1 and Type 2 statistical errors (false positives and false negatives, respectively).

The decision-making applications are consistent with the idea that every measurement is made to aid in the making of a decision [25], but the decisions happen at the ends of traceability chains. To properly quantify measurement uncertainty at these points, users require, at least, summary information on the long list of dispersive effects (see [6, Sec 3.3.2]) affecting their measurements, their instrument calibrations, and any realisations of standards, traced back to the definitions of the appropriate measurement units or documentary standards. Thus, the purpose of the other class of applications for measurement uncertainty is to model measurements and propagate uncertainty. For this purpose, and following the utility of equation (5), dispersion effects are almost universally characterised by variances or standard deviations. We use standard deviations formally for the standard uncertainties rather than variances because they have the same units as the dispersed quantities and are proportional to the widths of distributions.

Thus, there are two broad purposes for measurement uncertainty: modelling and decision making. The two purposes use measures that correspond closely with the standard and expanded uncertainties defined by the GUM. Table 1 identifies the properties of the two GUM-defined uncertainties in the context of the two purposes. When compared in this way, it becomes clear that the two types of uncertainty have very different natures and purposes.

The identification of the two purposes confirms some common uncertainty practices and clarifies others. For example, calibrations are performed to provide links in traceability chains by “...establishing a relation between the quantity values with measurement uncertainties provided by measurement standards and corresponding indications with associated measurement uncertainties, ...” [26]. This is modelling, and for modelling applications, the standard uncertainty is the proper measure. Additionally, because standard uncertainties are required for all downstream applications and expanded uncertainties are not, it is essential that calibration certificates provide unambiguous statements of standard uncertainties. This rationale explains the BIPM’s decision to report only standard uncertainties on its calibration certificates [4].

Table 1. The contrasting attributes and purposes of standard and expanded uncertainties.

Purpose	Modelling	Decision Making
Uncertainty Measure	Standard uncertainty	Expanded uncertainty
Description	Parameter in a model characterising the dispersion of measured values	An interval characterising the range of values reasonably attributed to the measurand
Nature	A standard deviation	Half-width of a confidence interval
Subject	A measurement system, process, or instrument	A measurand
Utilization	Used throughout traceability chains	Used at the ends of traceability chains
Symbol	u	$\pm U$

The different nature of the two uncertainties explains the GUM guidance that expanded uncertainties may be reported with a \pm symbol, but standard uncertainties should not. The distinction is important because of the risks of misinterpreting $\pm u$ as a confidence interval (with a specific coverage probability) and of applying the uncertainty to the measurand rather than the measurement process.

There are other considerations leading to the same conclusions. First, because expanded uncertainties are used to make decisions at the ends of traceability chains and are usually associated with the costs of Type 1 and Type 2 statistical errors specific to the user of the measurements, the user should determine the required balance of probabilities, and therefore also the level of confidence and coverage factor. It is not the responsibility of the test or calibration laboratory alone to determine appropriate coverage factors.

The use of expanded uncertainties for calibration certificates is reminiscent of a cipher. To calculate a standard uncertainty from an expanded uncertainty it is necessary to have three additional pieces of information—the effective degrees of freedom, the type of distribution, and the confidence level—and omission or corruption of any of them may lead to large errors in the calculated standard deviation, potentially weakening traceability chains.

Calibration laboratories may of course report both uncertainties, and there are a few cases where expanded uncertainties may be required—for example, when instruments are calibrated to be selected or validated for some prescribed purpose or tested for conformance to a documentary standard.

These observations suggest a couple of mysteries: why do most calibration certificates currently report expanded uncertainties (when practically no-one needs them); and why are they reported at a nominal 95% confidence level? There are two plausible explanations, and probably both are true. The practice dates to the 1920s when the statistician R. A. Fisher first developed significance testing. In an example, he chose 95% as a ‘reasonable’ level of significance, and that single precedent has been all but frozen into significance testing ever since. One of Fisher’s students later set the record straight [27]: “...[Fisher] does not recommend any fixed level of significance but suggests that the observed level of significance has to be used with other evidence that the experimenter may have in making a decision.”

Secondly, one of the reasons the 95% confidence level has survived may be that it is a ‘reasonable’ compromise between a highly discerning test and a test where the resulting confidence intervals and inferences are relatively insensitive to the nature of the distribution. In any case, the 95% number has been frozen into many documentary standards, including some for the specifications of measuring instruments.

Standard uncertainties are also the appropriate uncertainty measure for consensus values, as is current practice for CODATA and the BIPM when it reports reference values in *mises en pratique*, because consensus values are almost exclusively incorporated into other measurement models.

The situation is slightly more complicated for proficiency tests and measurement comparisons. The statistical analysis of a proficiency test is usually guided by a model [23], and therefore participants should report standard uncertainties, and the analysis should be carried out using standard uncertainties. But the uncertainty in the results of the comparison, on which decisions about the competence or otherwise of the participants is based, should be accompanied by the appropriate expanded uncertainties as defined by the test protocol.

The same guidance applies to scientific papers. Detailed analysis and uncertainty assessments should be in terms of the standard uncertainty, but where decisions are made, such as hypothesis tests, or when dealing with selection or validation of measurement processes or instruments, uncertainties based on expanded uncertainties with appropriate levels of confidence and coverage factors are appropriate.

We make the following additional recommendations. Firstly, the BIPM uncertainty guidance documents should be revised to give clear guidance on the purposes of measurement uncertainty. Without such guidance, many users and producers of measurements will have difficulty determining the fitness for purpose of different uncertainty statements, which may in turn affect the fitness for purpose of the measurements themselves.

Future revisions of ISO/IEC 17025 could usefully clarify the two purposes of measurement uncertainty. Standard uncertainties should always be reported on calibration certificates, and test reports should report uncertainties according to the needs of the user, which may be standard or expanded uncertainties, or both. Those involved with the plans to digitalise measurement reports should be especially aware of this point—as a minimum, standard uncertainties and degrees of freedom should always be reported.

For those teaching measurement, we encourage explanations of the purposes of measurement uncertainty: it is a tool for the management of risks and costs associated with decisions based on measurements. Careless or hurried assessments of uncertainty carry a risk of poor decisions, potentially resulting in significant financial costs or loss of life. Measurement models and well-informed uncertainty assessments are the glue that holds together traceability chains and, therefore, also the world’s measurement infrastructure. Finally, we note that these conclusions and recommendations are entirely consistent with the GUM, the VIM (the International Vocabulary of Metrology), and other CIPM and BIPM guides.

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